

Ferrosilicon alloys at the core of new thermal energy storage devices

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Abstract – Ferrosilicon alloys are ideal candidates to be used as phase change materials for thermal energy storage applications. This is because of their remarkably high latent heat of fusion (>1 MWh/m³) and low cost (< 5 €/kg). These characteristics are key to develop very cheap and compact energy storage devices. The use of these materials for energy storage applications is being investigated since 2017 in the frame of three EU projects. The first one, AMADEUS (2017-2019) established the basis for a technology. The project developed a lab-scale prototype that comprised silicon-boron alloys, for energy storage, combined with hybrid thermionic-photovoltaic generators, for thermal-to-electric energy conversion. Subsequently, two new EU projects started in 2022 to develop to specific applications for this technology. THERMOBAT (2022-2026) is developing a scaled up pre-industrial prototype that includes more than 100 L of FeSiB alloys, combined with a 1 kW thermophotovoltaic power generator. This prototype will store the surplus of renewable electricity generation and will produce combined heat and power on demand. The system will be tested in a sport center in Madrid in 2025 and will provide a fraction of the electricity and heat demands of the building. On the other hand, the SUNSON project (2022-2026) is developing a system that uses concentrated sunlight to melt a silicon alloy, thus storing solar energy in the form of latent heat, and subsequently, it produces electricity on demand, also using thermophotovoltaics. The project targets building a prototype with 10L of silicon alloy capacity, combined with 200 W of thermophotovoltaic electric power output. The prototype will be tested under real concentrated sunlight conditions at Plataforma Solar de Almería, in Spain. In this article I describe the general concept of latent heat thermophotovoltaic batteries, along with the state of the art in the two active EU projects (THERMOBAT and SUNSON).

1. INTRODUCTION

The drastic drop in prices of intermittent renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, is creating a new paradigm in the energy sector: there are increasingly more periods during which more electricity is produced than demanded, resulting in some of this electricity being wasted or sold at very low prices on the electricity market. Therefore, the next big challenge in the energy sector is to store the renewable energy surpluses and supply them when these resources are not available. Today's power storage capacity (~ 268 GW) accounts only for $\sim 3\%$ of current worldwide power generation capacity, being the vast majority (67%) pumped hydropower [1], which is geographically restricted. Therefore, the search for distributed and site-independent energy storage solutions is an urgent and important field of research today. Li-ion batteries, mainly utility-scale, accounts for most of the reminding 33 % of storage power capacity and are expected to grow in the upcoming years, driven by a drastic cost reduction, dropping from over 1000 €/kWh at the beginning of the 2010's to values close to 100 €/kWh this year. However, this cost is still high to enable the storage of the vast amounts of energy that will be needed to fully replace fossil fuels. Much cheaper options, in the range of few 10's of €/kWh are needed to enable the affordable storage of energy during periods longer than ~ 8 hours. In fact, several studies have shown that when the price of surplus electricity is very low and the amounts of energy to be stored are large, the priority is to reduce the storage system's cost, even if it means not recovering all the stored energy. These are known as long-duration

energy storage systems (LDES), and some paradigmatic examples include compressed air, hydrogen, flow batteries, or thermal energy storage.

Among all LDES options, thermal energy storage (TES) is particularly advantageous. The key is that storing energy in the form of heat is extremely cheap, up to 100 times cheaper than using current electrochemical batteries. Moreover, heat represents more than 50% of the world's energy demand and 40% of global CO₂ emissions. Thus, storing renewable energy in the form of heat would not only allow for substantial cost savings but also enable a larger fraction of the energy sector to be decarbonized, meeting part of this large thermal demand through renewable sources.

Thermal energy storage (TES) was initially developed in the field of concentrated solar power (CSP). CSP enables the direct storage of solar energy in the form of heat, which can be converted into electricity on demand. Today's CSP technology is largely based on the same concepts that have been used in large centralized thermal power plants since the start of the 20th Century [2]: the generated heat, produced in this case via concentrated solar energy, is converted into superheated steam to drive a conventional steam turbine that generates electricity. To store solar energy, the generated heat is used to warm a liquid, typically a molten salt, which flows from a "cold" tank at ~ 220 °C (minimum) to a "hot" tank at ~ 565 °C (maximum). The stored sensible heat in this liquid is later used to produce electricity when sunlight is not available. To reduce the cost, CSP research focuses on increasing the operational temperature of the system to lead to higher conversion efficiencies [2]. Typical steam Rankine cycles are limited in operation temperature to about 600 °C. Therefore, new engines (e.g. Brayton) and heat transfer fluids (HTF) that are stable at those temperatures (e.g. air or supercritical CO₂) [3] are being investigated. Other improvements are directed to use less amounts of building materials to save on materials cost (e.g. search for single-tank storage options) [4]. However, to make all these strategies profitable it is essential to progress through the learning curve of CSP technology, i.e. making installations. Unfortunately, this progress is being hindered by the requirement of very large initial investments of current CSP systems. Most of CSP plants require a power capacity larger than few 10's of MW to be profitable. These large sizes imply large initial capital expenditures (CAPEX), which added to the risk-averse of financiers on new technologies, result in hindering the investments.

Thermal Energy Storage (TES) has recently been reconsidered for storing surplus renewable electricity, resulting in the development of electro-thermal energy storage (ETES) or Power-to-Heat-to-Power (PHPS) systems. Numerous PHPS designs have emerged in the past few years, utilizing a diverse range of thermal storage materials such as stones, concrete, silicon, carbon, and ceramics. These systems operate over a wide temperature range, from approximately 500°C to over 2000°C, employing various thermal-to-electric energy converters [5], [6]. In contrast to conventional CSP systems, PHPS devices operating at ultra-high temperatures (above 1000°C) leverage the high enthalpy and energy density of stored heat [5], [7]. Most commercial systems aim to directly supply heat to industrial processes or use heat engines based on well-established thermodynamic cycles like Rankine, Brayton, or Stirling [8]. More innovative systems, like the ones discussed in this article, are based on thermophotovoltaic (TPV) generators. Designed to operate at extreme temperatures (>1000°C), TPV devices enable dense, modular, silent, and low-cost power generation, leading to very compact and scalable systems. PHPS systems that integrate TPV devices can use either solid [5] or liquid [9] sensible heat storage, as well as latent heat storage options [9].

Latent heat thermal energy storage solutions that operate at ultra-high temperatures (>1000°C) have been developed almost exclusively by two teams: the Australian startup 1414Degrees [8],

and an EU R&D consortium coordinated by IES-UPM since 2017 [10], [11]. Both teams use silicon or silicon alloys as phase change materials (PCM) for latent heat thermal energy storage. The following sections describe the R&D efforts within three EU-funded collaborative projects from 2017 to the present, focused on developing ultra-high temperature latent heat energy storage devices for both PHPS and solar thermal applications.

2. LATENT HEAT THERMOPHOTOVOLTAIC BATTERIES

The combination of latent heat energy storage and thermophotovoltaics was proposed for the first time in 1995 by Donald Chubb [12] and reassessed in 2013-2016 by researchers at the Solar Energy Institute of the Polytechnic University of Madrid (IES-UPM) [13], [14]. The original ideas consisted of storing concentrated sunlight in silicon [12], [13], a very abundant and cheap material (\$2/kg) that, when melted, can store 1.2 MWh per cubic meter of silicon as latent heat of fusion. This energy density is ten times higher than that of the molten salts used in solar thermal power plants and comparable to that of hydrogen pressurized to 500 atmospheres. The combination of low cost and high energy density of silicon allows energy to be stored at costs below €5/kWh (Figure 2).

However, the use of silicon has a serious limitation: it expands by about 10% when solidifying. This presents significant challenges for containment and jeopardizes the ability to achieve a large number of melting/solidification cycles, which are crucial for energy storage applications. Therefore, the original proposal by IES-UPM was to search for silicon alloys that exhibit negligible volume contraction upon solidification while retaining high latent heat and low cost. The initial proposal [14] involved alloying silicon with boron, as boron possesses even higher latent heat than silicon (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Volumetric cost and energy density of different thermal energy storage materials

Additionally, silicon melts at 1414°C, a much higher temperature than most known systems, necessitating the development of technologies capable of efficiently converting such high-temperature heat into electricity. This challenge led to the integration of thermophotovoltaic (TPV) devices into the concept. TPVs convert incandescent thermal radiation directly into electricity, functioning similarly to solar cells but using semiconductor materials that absorb infrared radiation, which is predominant in the thermal emission of hot bodies. Unlike conventional generators, a TPV converter does not need direct contact with the heat source to produce electricity. It can be positioned at a reasonable distance from the source, capturing its thermal emission. This capability allows the generation of electricity from thermal sources at

extremely high temperatures, offering a novel solution to the challenges posed by silicon's high melting point.

Moreover, the efficiency of TPV devices can be significantly increased, theoretically over 50%, by recycling the far-IR photons that are unable to produce electricity. This is achieved by incorporating a rear mirror in the cell, which reflects low-energy photons back to the thermal emitter for recycling (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Thermophotovoltaic energy conversion: spectral utilization and device structure (inset)

Although TPV cells were proposed in the early 1960s, the lack of high-quality semiconductor materials did not allow for high efficiencies to be achieved until relatively recently. In fact, during the last year, TPV cells capable of producing up to around 4.3 W/cm^2 (> 200 times more than a conventional solar cell) [15] and efficiencies over 40% [16] when illuminated with thermal sources between 1200 and 2400°C . Thus, TPV cells have already achieved efficiencies similar to those of conventional thermal engines (such as Stirling, Brayton, or Rankine cycles), although, unlike them, no moving parts, fluids, or heat exchangers are required. Therefore, the entire system can be made simpler, more economical, more compact, and quieter.

The proposal was to couple a TPV generator to a tank filled with silicon alloys at very high temperature ($>1200^\circ\text{C}$), previously melted using concentrated sunlight or an electric furnace powered by surplus renewable electricity, to produce electricity (and heat) on demand. This system has been called a "latent heat thermophotovoltaic battery," and on paper, it can achieve costs 100 times lower than current lithium-ion batteries [17].

2. AMADEUS PROJECT (2017-2019)

The first experimental developments took place between 2017 and 2019 within the framework of the European project AMADEUS, funded with €3.3 million by the European Innovation Council. Coordinated by IES-UPM, the main result was the first prototype of a thermophotovoltaic battery at laboratory scale (Figure 2a,b). Additionally, progress was made in optimizing and understanding some of its key components, such as TPV cells and silicon alloys, as well as the containers capable of housing these alloys at very high temperatures [10].

Within the AMADEUS project, both theoretical and experimental investigations by NTNU (Norway) focused on various compositions of Si-B and Si-B-X alloys. Particular attention was given to eutectic alloys such as Si-3.25B, Fe-26.38Si-9.35B, and Cr-43Si-5B, which showed the

most promising properties based on thermodynamic modeling with FactSage®. Among the studied alloys, Si-3.25B exhibited the highest latent heat in J/g, with a peak value of 1853 J/g, surpassing that of pure silicon. However, the ternary alloys Fe-26.38Si-9.35B and Cr-43Si-5B demonstrated higher latent heats per unit volume due to their greater weight density, making them more suitable for energy storage applications where volume is critical. Fe-26.38Si-9.35B emerged as the preferred alloy, given its use of abundant iron and a lower melting point, which reduces thermal insulation heat losses. This alloy showcased a record latent heat exceeding 4 kJ/cm³ at melting temperatures below 1220°C, the highest reported for temperatures below 1400°C [18], [19].

Figure 2: The different prototypes developed in AMADEUS (a, b) and THERMOBAT (c) projects.

Additionally, the reactivity of different liquid phase change materials (PCMs) with solid refractory materials for containers was assessed through wettability and thermal cyclability tests both at NTNU and the Foundry Research Institute (Poland). h-BN stood out as non-wettable and minimally reactive with all tested PCMs, particularly with Si-3.25B and Fe-26.38Si-9.35B alloys [20], [21]. Graphite, although well wetted by liquid Si and Si-xB, showed penetration and reactions forming SiC and B₄C, which could be manageable if equilibrium is achieved. Notably, Fe-26.38Si-9.35B did not penetrate graphite crucibles even after five days of testing, suggesting it as a promising candidate for practical applications. Graphite's high thermal diffusivity, measured at 13.3 mm²/s at 1200°C, makes it an attractive option for crucibles if its reactivity can be minimized. h-BN, with a moderately high thermal diffusivity of 4.63 mm²/s, presents a good alternative despite its higher cost. A conclusion of that project was that an appealing research direction involves developing advanced h-BN coatings on graphite to enhance performance. This is one of the objectives of the THERMOBAT project (discussed next), which aims to further optimize the use of these materials in practical energy storage applications.

The AMADEUS project also demonstrated the first experimental validation of TIPV (thermionic-photovoltaic) energy conversion. TIPV devices feature a tandem arrangement of a thermionic and a photovoltaic cell, with key components including a TIPV cathode (emitter) and an anode comprising a thermionic collector on the PV cell. The TIPV emitter radiates electrons and photons when heated, with electrons absorbed by the thermionic collector, generating electron-hole pairs in the PV cell and enhancing power density. Various thermionic emitters, such as lanthanum boride thin films, were developed by CNR (Italy), achieving a work function of ~2.6 eV and promising thermionic current densities at high temperatures.

For the anode, barium fluoride-based layers with low work functions were also optimized. GaAs and In_{0.53}Ga_{0.47}As semiconductors were fabricated at IES-UPM to fabricate TPV cells demonstrating high open-circuit voltages and photogenerated current densities. Two types of devices, two-terminal [22] and three-terminal [23] were developed for proof-of-concept experiments in a collaboration between CNR and IES-UPM.

3. THERMOBAT PROJECT (2022-2026)

THERMOBAT project started in June 2022, with €2.6 million from the European Innovation Council (EIC), to scale up the core technology developed in the AMADEUS project and manufacture a first electro-thermal battery based on those principles that can be used in a real application environment. To manufacture the prototype, the project includes partners with expertise in metallurgy (NTNU in Norway and Ferroglobe in Spain), refractory containers (Vesuvius-Foseco, Netherlands), electric furnaces (Entech, Sweden), and TPV generators (IES-UPM, Spain). The project also has the necessary partners to bring this technology to market: Thermophoton, a startup recently created by IES-UPM researchers, will be responsible for commercializing the systems, while Serveo will provide one of its buildings to install the system, becoming the first company to test this technology in a real environment and eventually one of the first customers of this technology.

Coordinated by IES-UPM, the consortium is manufacturing a prototype with a storage capacity of at least 100 kWh, which is about 200 times larger than the one developed in the previous project. The system will store surplus electricity from the grid and supply electricity and heat on demand to a building to reduce its energy bill. To achieve this, the project includes a technological development phase in which the various components of the system are being manufactured, from TPV generators to ferrosilicon alloys and their containers, to the thermal insulation and electric heating system, as well as the management and control system. Finally, all components will be integrated, tested in a controlled laboratory environment, and then installed in a building and monitored for several months. The prototype is expected to be ready by the end of 2024, and tests will be conducted throughout 2025.

The project's goal is to demonstrate the functionality of the system's basic minimum unit. However, to reach the market, it will be necessary to build systems with much larger storage capacities, at least 10 MWh. It is only at these scales that the technology becomes economically viable, as smaller systems will be penalized by considerable heat losses or, alternatively, by an unaffordable cost of the thermal insulation system. Therefore, the project will aim to prepare the technology for subsequent industrialization, establishing scalable and environmentally friendly manufacturing processes. In case of success, and after the project completion, these processes will be implemented by one of its industrial partners. For example, Ferroglobe is one of the world's largest producers of silicon alloys, and Vesuvius-Foseco is a world leader in the manufacture of refractory products.

3. SUNSON PROJECT (2022-2026)

SUNSON project started in December 2022, with €3 million from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), to develop a first prototype of a concentrated solar power (CSP) system based on the operational principles investigated in the AMADEUS project. To manufacture the prototype, the project includes partners with expertise in metallurgy (NTNU in Norway), solar concentration (Plataforma Solar de Almeria in Spain), artificial intelligence and simulations (IDENER, Spain), Environmental impact assessment (HOLOSS, Portugal), Mechanical design and engineering (IONVAC, Italy) and TPV generators (IES-UPM, Spain).

Coordinated by IES-UPM, the consortium will manufacture a solar-powered prototype with a storage capacity of 10 kWh. The system will store concentrated sunlight and supply electricity on demand using TPV devices. The goal is to achieve a very compact and modular CSP unit with an energy density 10 times greater than of current CSP options. To achieve this, the project will develop the various components of the system, from TPV generators to high silicon alloys, as well as the concentrator optical design. Finally, all components will be integrated, tested in a vertical solar furnace at Plataforma Solar de Almeria in Spain. The prototype is expected to be ready by mid-2025, and tests will be conducted throughout the end of 2025 and early 2026.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The rapid decrease in costs of intermittent renewable energy sources like solar and wind is creating a significant shift in the energy sector, resulting in periods of surplus electricity production. The primary challenge now lies in storing these surpluses efficiently to ensure a stable and reliable energy supply when renewable sources are unavailable. Among long-duration energy storage (LDES) options, thermal energy storage (TES) stands out due to its cost-effectiveness and ability to meet substantial portions of the world's thermal energy demand. TES was initially developed for concentrated solar power (CSP) systems, which store solar energy as heat and convert it to electricity on demand. Recent innovations have expanded TES applications to include electro-thermal energy storage (ETES) or Power-to-Heat-to-Power (PHPS) systems, which utilize various materials and operate at high temperatures to maximize energy density and conversion efficiency.

Research and development efforts, particularly within EU-funded projects like AMADEUS, THERMOBAT, and SUNSON, have focused on advancing latent heat thermophotovoltaic batteries using high-temperature phase-change materials like ferrosilicon alloys. These projects aim to demonstrate the feasibility and economic viability of these innovative storage systems, progressing from laboratory prototypes to real-world applications. The success of these initiatives could significantly lower energy storage costs, facilitate the broader adoption of renewable energy, and contribute to the decarbonization of the energy sector.

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